

Putih, and Tilockkachari had high infection by either RTBV alone or RTBV + RTSV.

The very low symptoms on these varieties (average score 2.5), despite high infection by RTV-associated viruses, indicate tolerance for tungro. The varieties exhibited less than 10% reduction in plant height and no leaf discoloration, despite infection by either RTBV alone or RTBV + RTSV.

Other varieties that had intermediate to susceptible reactions had high infection. Susceptible check TN1 had an average severity index score of 8.9 and 98.3% infection by RTBV + RTSV combined.

These results indicate the importance of scoring RTV infection not only on the basis of symptoms, but also through serology. □

Reaction of selected varieties to rice tungro-associated viruses, using the improved mass screening method and ELISA. IRRI, 1989.

Variety	Acc. no.	Average severity index ^a	Plants (%) infected with		
			RTBV	RTSV	RTBV + RTSV
TN1	-	8.9	1.7	0.0	98.3
Utri Rajapan	16684	2.9	45.0	3.7	32.7
ARC11554	21473	1.9	10.0	0.0	0.0
Pankhari 203	5999	2.7	76.0	1.7	0.0
ASD7	6303	5.7	44.7	0.0	6.7
Balimau Putih	17204	2.1	0.0	19.3	61.7
ASD8	6393	6.1	44.7	0.0	6.3
TKM6	237	5.9	89.7	0.0	0.0
Utri Merah	16680	2.5	6.0	0.0	0.0
Jhingasail	8336	6.2	19.3	2.0	78.7
Goria	26345	4.7	63.3	0.0	28.3
Choron Bawla	26323	4.4	45.0	0.0	49.3
Tilockkachari	8321	2.3	21.7	1.7	3.3
Kashiabinni	37488	4.2	50.3	1.7	1.7
Palasithari 601	12069	4.9	83.7	0.0	0.0

^a Scale and descriptions: 1 = no symptoms, 3 = 1-10% plant height reduction with no leaf discoloration, 5 = 11-30% plant height reduction with no distinct leaf discoloration, 7 = 31-50% plant height reduction and/or yellow to orange leaf discoloration, 9 = more than 50% plant height reduction and yellow to orange leaf discoloration.

Production of helper component in rice tungro virus (RTSV)-infected plants

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Rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) are transmitted by the green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens*. RTBV can be acquired and transmitted only by GLH that have fed on RTSV-source plants. RTSV particles do not bear the helper function for RTBV transmission, but a hypothetical helper compo-

nent is produced in RTSV-infected plants.

We exposed 7-d-old TN1 seedlings transplanted in pots separately to four or five RTSV-viruliferous GLH for 12-h inoculation feeding. At 0, 12, 24, 36, 48, 60, 72, 84, 96, and 108 h after RTSV inoculation, a seedling was confined in a cage with a batch of virus-free GLH adults for 12 h. Then, the batch of GLH was given 10-12 h inoculation feeding on TN1 plants infected with RTBV alone. After that acquisition feeding, individual GLH were given a 1-d inoculation feeding on a 7-d-old TN1 seedling in a test tube.

One month after inoculation, seedlings were indexed by ELISA for the presence of RTBV and RTSV.

GLH that fed on RTSV-inoculated plants 36 h and longer after inoculation transmitted RTBV (see table). GLH that fed on RTSV-source plants at 72 h and longer after inoculation, then on RTBV-source plants, were infective for both RTBV and RTBV + RTSV.

These results indicate that RTSV-infected plants began to serve as a source for the helper component 36 h after inoculation and as a source for tungro 72 h after inoculation. □

Transmission of RTBV and RTSV to TN1 seedlings after a 1-d feeding by GLH that had fed 12 h on RTSV source plants 0 to 108 h after a 12-h inoculation feeding by RTSV-viruliferous GLH and then for 12 h on RTBV source plants IRRI, 1989.

Feeding sequence			GLH (no.) tested	GLH (no.) that transmitted		
1st (12 h) ^a	2d (12 h)	Inoculation (24 h)		RTBV	RTBV+ RTSV	RTSV
RTSV (12)	RTBV	TN1	35	0	0	0
RTSV (24)	RTBV	TN1	32	0	0	0
RTSV (36)	RTBV	TN1	44	3	0	0
RTSV (48)	RTBV	TN1	37	3	2	0
RTSV (60)	RTBV	TN1	23	2	0	0
RTSV (72)	RTBV	TN1	25	3	3	0
RTSV (84)	RTBV	TN1	32	4	3	0
RTSV (96)	RTBV	TN1	30	6	6	1
RTSV (108)	RTBV	TN1	27	5	3	3

^a Number in parentheses indicates hours after inoculation with RTSV.

Effect of vector resistance on tungro (RTV) transmission

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Predominant rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) transmission by RTV-viruliferous green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* has been observed in GLH-resistant IR varieties. We examined this contradiction using GLH-resistant and susceptible cultivars.

ARC11554, IR5492, IR74, and IR36 were given six sequential 4-h inocula-

tion access feedings alternately with TN1, using male or female GLH adults. For the control, GLH were tested successively on TN1 and IR5492.

Two trials were conducted, using 80 RTV-viruliferous GLH per variety. Three weeks after inoculation, plants were indexed for RTBV and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) by the latex test.

With alternate feeding, GLH transmitted mainly RTBV alone on highly resistant ARC11554, IR5492, and IR74. On moderately resistant IR36 and susceptible TN1, either RTBV + RTSV or RTBV alone was transmitted (see figure). Transmission by GLH decreased with increases in inoculation feeding time.

GLH retained virus infectivity throughout six alternate feedings on ARC11554, IR5492, IR74, IR36, and TN1 and throughout six serial feedings on TN1, but lost infectivity after two successive feedings on IR5492.

Alternate feeding did not demonstrate any effect of GLH feeding on highly resistant varieties and their transmission of the virus in subsequent feedings on susceptible TN1, except for RTBV transmission in highly resistant varieties. □

Infection of RTBV and RTSV in ARC1 1554, IR74, IR36, and IR5492 plants after 6 sequential 4-h inoculation feedings alternately on TN1 (a to d) and in succession in GLH- and RTV-susceptible TN1 and GLH-resistant IR5492 plants (e and f).

Inheritance of resistance to bacterial blight (BB) in rice

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Yunnan, one of the centers of origin of *Oryza sativa* L., may also be a center of resistance genes. We screened 96 cultivars from Yunnan for resistance to BB *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*. Traditional cultivar Yunnan Dali was found to be resistant (Table 1).

The mode of inheritance of Yunnan Dali's resistance to a bacterial strain from Jiangling 691, a representative rice and isolate in central China, was studied. We analyzed the F₁, F₂, and F₃ populations from crosses of Yunnan Dali and three other cultivars. With susceptible Guangluai 4, Yunnan Dali

Table 1. Type, origin, and BB resistance reaction of rice cultivars in Yunnan, China. 1986.

Cultivar	Type	Origin	Score	
			1985 ^a	1986 ^b
Yunnan Dali	Japonica	Yunnan	3.3	3.5
IR28	Indica	IRRI	2.0	1.0
Nankeng 15	Japonica	Jiangsu	1.5	1.0
Guangluai 4	Indica	Guangdong	9.0	9.0

^aFor 26 plants. ^bFor 30 plants.

Table 2. Classification of F₁ and F₂ plants for BB from crosses of Yunnan Dali with resistant and susceptible cultivars. Yunnan, China, 1986.

Cross	F ₁ score	F ₂			Xc ²
		R	S	T	
Yunnan Dali/Guangluai 4	8.0	36	394	430	2.935 (1:15)
Yunnan Dali/IR28	1.0	371	103	474	0.089 (49:15)
Yunnan Dali/Nankeng 15	1.0	358	107	464	0.026 (49:15)

resistance is controlled by two recessive genes with overlapping effects (Table 2). It is not allelic with the dominant

genes in IR28 and Nankeng 15 and is not allelic with *xa-5*, *xa-8*, and *xa-9* genes. These are two new genes. □